

Research article

Quantitative criteria for the validity of the elastic half-space assumption in AFM nanoindentation

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ABSTRACT

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is a widely employed technique for nanoscale mechanical characterization of biological and soft materials. Typically, contact mechanics models used to extract the Young's modulus assume that the sample behaves as an elastic half-space. However, this assumption can break down when the lateral dimensions of the sample are limited or when indentation depths become significant. In this study, the limits of the elastic half-space approximation in AFM spherical indentation are investigated through analytical modeling, finite element method (FEM) simulations (performed in Ansys® Academic Research Mechanical, 2025 R1), and AFM nanoindentation experiments on agarose gels. The analytical results reveal two distinct deformation regimes—shallow ($h \leq 0.1 R$) and deep ($h \leq 0.6 R$) indentation—and show that the minimum lateral sample dimension required to satisfy half-space conditions ranges from approximately 1.7 to 8 times the indenter radius, depending on indentation depth. FEM simulations corroborate these findings by visualizing the lateral extent of deformation fields under increasing loads. The results provide quantitative criteria for the applicability of classical contact models and underscore the necessity of accounting for sample geometry in AFM-based biomechanical measurements.

1. Introduction

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) has become a crucial technique for investigating the mechanical properties of biological materials at the nanoscale. One of the key advantages of AFM lies in its ability to perform measurements in liquid environments that closely mimic physiological conditions, making it particularly well-suited for studies involving living cells and tissues [1,2]. With its remarkable spatial resolution—reaching sub-nanometer levels—and its capacity to apply and measure forces in the pico-newton range, AFM provides an unparalleled window into the mechanical behavior and structural integrity of biological systems. This level of sensitivity enables researchers to detect subtle molecular-level changes, track compositional variations, and investigate dynamic processes such as cell–cell interactions and matrix remodeling during the progression of diseases [3–5].

Over the past decade, AFM has gained recognition as a powerful nano-diagnostic platform. Its quantitative capabilities have enabled the development of objective biomechanical markers that distinguish

between healthy and pathological tissues, contributing to more accurate and earlier diagnosis [6]. Furthermore, AFM facilitates real-time, minimally invasive observation of ultrastructural features, cellular deformation, and single-molecule events, thereby offering profound insights into the complex mechanical landscape of biological systems under both normal and diseased states [7].

In addition, AFM has found extensive application in biomedical research, particularly in the early detection and diagnosis of cancer. One of its most prominent uses is the mechanical characterization of cells, where it has proven especially valuable due to its ability to reveal significant differences in stiffness between normal and cancerous cells [8–17]. Among the key parameters measured by AFM is Young's modulus, which serves as an effective biomarker for distinguishing healthy from malignant cells based on their distinct elastic properties [8]. Numerous studies have validated the potential of AFM in cancer diagnostics by examining tissue samples across a spectrum of pathological states—including normal, benign, and malignant specimens [18–23]. Beyond oncology, AFM has also shown promise in the

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diagnosis of other medical conditions. Its sensitivity to mechanical alterations in biological structures has enabled its use in the detection of degenerative diseases such as osteoarthritis [24,25] and neurodegenerative disorders like Alzheimer's disease [26–29]. These applications highlight the broader diagnostic utility of AFM, which extends beyond cancer and provides a versatile tool for assessing a wide range of disease-induced biomechanical changes [30].

It is also important to note that AFM has been extensively used to mechanically characterize a wide range of micro- and nanoscale features, including proteins, small biological fibrils such as amyloid fibrils, lipid membranes, and viruses [31–42]. In most cases involving purely elastic contact using spherical indenters and low indentation rates, the Hertz model is employed for data processing to derive the Young's modulus at the point of interest [43,44]:

$$F = \frac{4}{3} \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} R^{1/2} h^{3/2}, \quad (1)$$

where, F is the applied force on the material of interest, h is the indentation depth, R is the indenter's radius (Fig. 1) and E , ν are the Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the material respectively. Eq. (1) is valid when the indenter is several orders of magnitude stiffer than the tested sample, an assumption that is reasonable when testing soft biological materials with typical AFM indenters. A major limitation of Eq. (1) is that the indentation depth should be significantly smaller than the indenter's radius ($h \ll R$) [45]. The exact equations for deep spherical indentations were derived by Sneddon are presented below [46,47]:

$$F = \frac{E}{2(1-\nu^2)} \left[(r_c^2 + R^2) \ln \left(\frac{R+r_c}{R-r_c} \right) - 2r_c R \right], \quad (2)$$

where r_c is the contact radius between the indenter and the sample (Fig. 1). The relationship between indentation depth, contact radius, and tip radius is described by the following equation [46,47]:

$$\ln \left(\frac{R+r_c}{R-r_c} \right) = \frac{2h}{r_c}. \quad (3)$$

However, Eqs. (2) and (3) do not provide a direct relationship between the applied force and the indentation depth, making the fitting process challenging. To facilitate data processing in AFM indentation experiments, an alternative equation has been previously derived [47]:

$$F = \frac{4ER^{\frac{1}{2}}}{3(1-\nu^2)} h^{\frac{3}{2}} \left[c_1 + \sum_{M=2}^N \frac{3}{2M} c_M R^{\frac{3}{2}-M} h^{M-3/2} \right]. \quad (4)$$

In Eq. (4), c_1, c_2, \dots, c_M are constants that depend on the h/R ratio. For conventional indentation experiments, retaining the first three terms in Eq. (4) yields sufficiently accurate results, as they closely match Sneddon's solution for cases where $h/R < 1.32$:

Fig. 1. A rigid sphere of radius R indenting an elastic half-space. The indentation depth is denoted by h , and the contact radius by r_c . The radial distance from the center of the sphere is represented by r .

$$F = \frac{4ER^{\frac{1}{2}}}{3(1-\nu^2)} h^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(c_1 + \frac{3}{4} c_2 R^{-1/2} h^{1/2} + \frac{3}{6} c_3 R^{-3/2} h^{3/2} \right), \quad (5)$$

where, $c_1 = 1.022$, $c_2 = -0.1133$ and $c_3 = -0.0742$ [47].

Another major limitation of equations presented in this paper is that they are valid for the case of an elastic half-space. An elastic half-space is an idealized model representing a homogeneous, isotropic, and linearly elastic material that occupies an infinite volume beneath a flat surface, extending infinitely in all directions except upward, where it has a free, flat boundary. However, this is not the case in real AFM indentation experiments. Soft biological samples at the nanoscale are heterogeneous; therefore, several models have been proposed to account for the true nature of these materials [48–51]. It is important to note that classical equations, such as (1) and (4), can be extended to cases resulting in an 'apparent' or 'average' Young's modulus [48–51]. Another important issue concerns the dimensions of a specific sample or subfeature at the nanoscale. In many experimental cases, the AFM tip apex, modeled as a sphere [52], interacts with a specific subfeature on the sample (e.g., a protein, fibril, or virus) whose dimensions are on the same order of magnitude as the tip apex. A critical question in these cases is whether the sample can be considered "large" compared to the tip radius, allowing it to be treated as a half-space. The purpose of this paper is to combine simple physical considerations with Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations to identify the critical threshold beyond which the elastic half-space assumption becomes invalid.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 (Materials and Methods) outlines the general principles underlying the fundamental physical considerations and the Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations conducted in this study. It also describes the protocol for AFM nanoindentation experiments on agarose gels, which can be reasonably approximated as elastic half-spaces. Section 3 (Results) outlines the mathematical calculations used to provide a first approximation of the validity of the elastic half-space assumption for both small and large indentation depths. In addition, the results of the FEM analysis are presented for various cases of samples with lateral dimensions comparable to the radius of the indenter. The force-indentation curves obtained from these samples are compared with theoretical models of spherical indentation on an elastic half-space, as well as with experimental results obtained from agarose gels. Section 4 (Discussion) presents an overview of the assumptions used in the FEM simulations and highlights the key results derived in this study.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Physical considerations

For a preliminary evaluation of the applicability of the elastic half-space approximation in AFM nanoindentation, we analyzed the deflection profile of an elastic surface indented by a rigid spherical probe. The vertical displacement outside the contact area is described by a dimensionless function $\Omega(r)$, where r is the radial coordinate (see Fig. 1) derived from classical contact mechanics theory, which captures the surface deformation beyond the contact radius. This function allowed us to examine how the deflection decays with increasing distance from the contact region. Evaluations were conducted for both small ($h \leq 0.1R$) and larger ($h \leq 0.6R$) indentation depths relative to the indenter's radius.

2.2. FEA modelling

The nanoindentation problem was simulated utilizing the finite-element method through Ansys® Academic Research Mechanical, 2025 R1 software by constructing a two-dimensional, axisymmetric representation of a spherical indenter penetrating an elastic specimen (Fig. 2). The indenter was modeled as a rigid body featuring a spherical

Fig. 2. The axisymmetric geometry that was utilized to model the problem of indentation of elastic half-space (shown dimensions are not in scale).

tip of radius $R = 0.001$ mm ($1 \mu\text{m}$), whereas the specimen was modeled as a homogeneous, isotropic block whose lateral (L_r) and vertical extents (L_z) were initially set to at least ten times the indenter radius to minimize the influence of artificial edge constraints; these dimensions were later varied parametrically up to $10R$, enabling a systematic assessment of boundary-effect sensitivity.

By exploiting axisymmetry, only the meridional half-section needed to be meshed, effectively halving the number of elements and substantially reducing computational cost without sacrificing physical fidelity. The geometry was meshed utilizing quadrilateral elements. After a series of preliminary simulations it was found that the results show no variation when elements of size $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ or less were used (Fig. 3). To this end, all simulation presented in this paper performed in a mesh comprised of elements of size $0.05 \mu\text{m}$. The mesh used for our numerical simulation is shown in Fig. 4 (notice that for viewing clarity only a part of the mesh near the contact point is shown in the figure).

Material characterization played a central role in accurately capturing mechanical response. The indenter material was assigned linear-elastic properties representative of ultra-hard materials, with Young's modulus $E = 240$ GPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.28$. In contrast, the specimen was defined by an ideal elastic constitutive law: Young's modulus was set to $E = 0.10$ MPa (100 kPa), Poisson's ratio to $\nu = 0.5$. This stark disparity in stiffness ensured that deformation occurred within the specimen, thereby mimicking the rigid-indenter assumption commonly adopted in nanoindentation experiments.

The mechanical interaction between the indenter and specimen was defined as a surface-to-surface contact pair. A frictionless tangential law was prescribed in order to isolate pure normal indentation behavior and prevent any tangential load transfer. The Augmented Lagrange algorithm [53] was utilized to enforce impenetrability in the normal direction, balancing the need for strict contact constraints against the potential for numerical instability. This formulation ensured that the indenter could freely slide without resistance while accurately transmitting normal compressive forces to the specimen.

Boundary conditions were applied to mimic an ideally supported

Fig. 3. Force versus indentation depth curve for two different element sizes. The results are independent of the element size when the mesh is comprised of elements of size 10^{-7} m (the case of 10^{-7} m is not shown to not clutter the plot) or less. ($L_z = L_r = 10R$).

Fig. 4. A typical mesh comprised of quadrilateral elements of size $0.05 \mu\text{m}$. Only a portion of the mesh near contact region is shown. (Image used courtesy of ANSYS, Inc.).

specimen and to preserve the axisymmetric simplification. All degrees of freedom at the bottom edge of the specimen were constrained—translational (both radial and axial) and rotational—to represent a perfectly rigid support. Along the central axis of symmetry, radial displacement was set to zero, thereby enforcing the geometric constraint of axisymmetry. The indenter itself was treated as a rigid-body entity permitted only axial translation; lateral displacements and all rotations were suppressed to conform with the intended kinematic scenario.

2.3. AFM experiments on agarose gels

AFM nanoindentation measurements were performed using colloidal probes (CP-PNPL-BSG-A, sQube; sourced from NanoAndMore GMBH) featuring spherical tips with a nominal radius of $1 \mu\text{m}$. Prior to data acquisition, the probes were calibrated against a TGT1 AFM calibration grating (NT-MDT Instruments). The experimental substrate consisted of 2.5 % agarose gels prepared in 35 mm Petri dishes. Due to their high-water content, the gels were modeled as incompressible materials with

a Poisson’s ratio of $\nu = 0.5$. A ramp frequency of $\sim 1\text{--}2$ Hz was employed during the AFM nanoindentation experiments, which is within the recommended range for soft biological materials [54]. This choice minimizes potential viscoelastic effects, ensuring that the measured Young’s modulus reflects the quasi-static elastic response of the agarose gel. Young’s modulus was extracted from the force–indentation data using the AtomicJ software [55].

3. Results

3.1. Physical considerations. Revisiting the half-space assumption in spherical indentation

To preliminarily assess the validity of the elastic half-space approximation in AFM nanoindentation, we examined the surface deflection profile resulting from indentation by a rigid spherical probe. Consider

the case of a rigid sphere indenting an elastic half-space. The deflection of the elastic plane within the contact area between the sphere and the sample ($0 \leq r \leq r_c$) is given by the following equation [56]:

$$y_{in}(r) = r_c P_0 \frac{(1 - \nu^2)}{2E} \frac{\pi}{2} \left[2 - \left(\frac{r}{r_c} \right)^2 \right] \tag{6}$$

where,

$$P_0 = \frac{3}{2} \frac{F}{\pi r_c^2} \tag{7}$$

Outside the contact area ($r > r_c$), the deflection of the elastic surface is defined as follows:

Fig. 5. $\Omega = f(x')$ graphs for the domains $0.32 \leq x' \leq 2$ (Figure a), $0.32 \leq x' \leq 4$ (Figure b), $0.32 \leq x' \leq 6$ (Figure c) and $0.32 \leq x' \leq 8$ (Figure d) and small indentation depths. A sample whose lateral dimensions are only four times larger than the tip radius can still be approximated as an elastic half-space, as the surface deflection at $r = 4 R$ is just 7 % of that at the contact radius.

$$y_{\text{out}}(r) = r_c P_0 \frac{(1 - \nu^2)}{2E} \left\{ \left[2 - \left(\frac{r}{r_c} \right)^2 \right] \arcsin \left(\frac{r_c}{r} \right) + \left[\left(\frac{r}{r_c} \right)^2 - 1 \right]^{1/2} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Eqs. (6) and (8) lead to the same result when $r = r_c$:

$$y_{\text{in}} = y_{\text{out}} = y_o = r_c P_0 \frac{(1 - \nu^2)}{2E} \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (9)$$

A simple approach to approximate the area deformed by a sphere indenting an elastic half-space is presented below. First, consider the following function:

$$\Omega(r) = \left[2 - \left(\frac{r}{r_c} \right)^2 \right] \arcsin \left(\frac{r_c}{r} \right) + \left[\left(\frac{r}{r_c} \right)^2 - 1 \right]^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

Therefore, Eq. (8) is modified as follows:

$$y_{\text{out}}(r) = r_c P_0 \frac{(1 - \nu^2)}{2E} \Omega(r) \quad (11)$$

Clearly, as if $\Omega(r) \rightarrow 0$, $y_{\text{out}}(r) \rightarrow 0$. Eq. (10) can be easily modified and written with respect to the ratio r/R . The contact radius for small indentation depths (i.e. $h \leq R/10$) is given by the simple equation $r_c = \sqrt{Rh}$ [57]. Therefore, considering a maximum indentation depth equal to $h = R/10$, $r_c = R/\sqrt{10}$. Hence:

$$\frac{r}{R} = \frac{r}{\sqrt{10}r_c} \quad (12)$$

We will use the symbol d for r/r_c and x' for r/R . For $d = 1$, $x' = 0.32$. Using Eq. (12), it is trivial to calculate x' (i.e., the ratio r/R) for each value of x . In Fig. 5, we present the $\Omega = f(x')$ graphs for the domain $0.32 \leq x' \leq 2$ (Fig. 5-a)), $0.32 \leq x' \leq 4$ (Fig. 5-b)), $0.32 \leq x' \leq 6$ (Fig. 5-c)) and $0.32 \leq x' \leq 8$ (Fig. 5-d)).

For $x' = 2$, $\Omega = 0.21$. This equals to 13 % of the initial Ω -value. For $x' = 4$, $\Omega = 0.11$ (~7 % of the initial Ω -value), for $x' = 6$, $\Omega = 0.07$ (~4 % of the initial Ω -value) and for $x' = 8$, $\Omega = 0.05$ (~3 % of the initial Ω -value). The aforementioned results suggest that for small indentation depths ($h < R/10$), a material with lateral dimensions only four times greater than the tip radius can be approximated as an elastic half-space, since the surface deflection at $r = 4R$ is only 7 % of that at the contact radius. This result will also be tested in Section 3.2 using FEM simulations. The elastic half-space approximation strongly depends on the maximum indentation depth. We will now explore the same approximation for deeper indentations.

For deep spherical indentations the contact radius is related with indentation depth using the following equation (under the restriction $0 \leq h/R \leq 1.32$) [47]:

$$\frac{r_c}{R} = c_1 \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^{1/2} + c_2 \frac{h}{R} + c_3 \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

where, $c_1 = 1.022$, $c_2 = -0.1133$ and $c_3 = -0.0742$ [47].

In addition,

$$x' = \frac{r}{r_c} = \frac{r}{c_1 (hR)^{1/2} + c_2 R + c_3 \frac{h^2}{R}} \quad (14)$$

In this paper, we do not consider cases involving very large indentations (e.g., $h > R$), where the assumption of purely elastic behavior may no longer hold. Such large deformations can lead to nonlinear elastic responses or irreversible material changes, which are beyond the scope of this study. Considering a maximum indentation depth equal to $h = 0.6R$, we conclude in $r_c = 0.65R$. Thus, Eq. (14) is simplified as below:

$$\frac{r}{R} = 0.65 \frac{r}{r_c} \quad (15)$$

For $d = 1$, $x' = 0.65$, using Eq. (15), it is trivial to calculate x' for each

value of x . In Fig. 6 we present the $\Omega = f(x')$ graphs for the domain $0.65 \leq x' \leq 2$ (Fig. 6-a)), $0.65 \leq x' \leq 4$ (Fig. 6-b)), $0.65 \leq x' \leq 6$ (Fig. 6-c)) and $0.65 \leq x' \leq 8$ (Fig. 6-d)). For $x' = 2$, $\Omega = 0.44$. This equals to 28 % of the initial Ω -value. For $x' = 4$, $\Omega = 0.22$ (~14 % of the initial Ω -value), for $x' = 6$, $\Omega = 0.15$ (~9 % of the initial Ω -value) and for $x' = 8$, $\Omega = 0.11$ (~7 % of the initial Ω -value). Therefore, at greater indentation depths, only samples with substantially larger dimensions can be reasonably approximated as elastic half-spaces. The deformation beyond the contact area becomes minimal—approximately 7 % of that at the contact radius—only when the sample's lateral dimensions reach $8R$. These findings suggest that for large indentation depths ($h \leq 0.6R$), a material with lateral dimensions at least eight times the indenter tip radius can be effectively treated as an elastic half-space, since the surface deflection at $r = 8R$ decreases to just 7 % of the deflection at the contact radius.

3.2. FEM simulations

In this section, simulations were performed using a rigid spherical indenter on elastic samples of finite lateral dimensions. This setup enables a systematic investigation of the elastic half-space assumption by analyzing how changes in the sample's lateral size affects the indentation response. Focusing exclusively on elastic behavior and controlled geometry, the goal is to determine the critical lateral dimensions required for the half-space model to remain valid across different indentation depths. Specifically, cylindrical samples with radii ranging from $L_r = 2R$ to $L_r = 10R$; in all cases $L_z = 10R$ was used to eliminate substrate effects. Force-indentation curves were recorded to characterize the mechanical response and evaluate the validity of the elastic half-space approximation for samples with finite lateral sizes.

Fig. 7 depicts the interface deformation near the contact point for varying applied forces (refer to Section 2.2 for simulation parameters used). The vertical displacements are shown for increasing indentation forces. As the applied force increases, a progressive increase in both the contact area and the surrounding deformation is observed. The displacement field, represented by the color scale, reveals the spatial distribution of vertical deformation, with maximum displacements concentrated beneath the indenter and diminishing radially. These results illustrate the elastic response of the soft sample and highlight how increased loading affects the deformation extent and magnitude near the contact zone.

Fig. 8 illustrates the evolution of the free surface profile for different applied forces during spherical indentation. As the indentation force increases, the deformation becomes more pronounced and extends further laterally, clearly demonstrating the response of the elastic material. These simulations provide insight into the localized nature of deformation near the contact area and how it scales with force magnitude.

To evaluate the accuracy of the numerical simulations, we compared the resulting force-indentation data with experimental AFM measurements obtained on an agarose gel characterized by a Young's modulus of approximately 100 kPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.5. We performed $N = 16$ force-indentation measurements on the agarose gel. The measured Young's modulus values had a mean of 98.75 kPa, with a sample standard deviation of 3.70 kPa and a sample variance of 13.71 kPa² (calculated using Bessel's correction, $N - 1$ in the denominator). These values indicate low relative variability (coefficient of variation approximately equal to 3.75 %), confirming the robustness of the experimental results. In Fig. 9, we present the force-indentation curve of a representative measurement, for which the Young's modulus was approximately 101 kPa, illustrating the quality and reliability of the data.

Additionally, theoretical force-indentation data were calculated using Eq. (4), employing the same maximum indentation depth and identical material properties. These theoretical results are also included in Fig. 9 for direct comparison. The close agreement among the

Fig. 6. $\Omega = f(x')$ graphs for the domains $0.65 \leq x' \leq 2$ (Figure a), $0.65 \leq x' \leq 4$ (Figure b), $0.65 \leq x' \leq 6$ (Figure c) and $0.65 \leq x' \leq 8$ (Figure d) and large indentation depths. A sample whose lateral dimensions is at least eight times larger than the tip radius can be approximated as an elastic half-space for large indentations ($h \leq 0.6 R$).

simulation, experimental, and theoretical data confirms that the numerical model accurately captures the elastic contact behavior between the rigid spherical indenter and the sample surface.

To investigate the influence of the sample's lateral dimensions on the force-indentation response, a series of simulations was performed using lateral dimensions ranging from $L_r = 2R$ to $L_r = 10R$. The results presented in Fig. 10a indicate that for small indentation depths, a lateral dimension of approximately $4R$ is sufficient to approximate the sample as an elastic half-space. The reason is that the force-indentation data are nearly identical for $L_r \geq 4R$ at small indentation depths, indicating that the influence of the sample's lateral dimensions is negligible in this regime. However, for larger indentation depths, the half-space assumption remains valid only when the lateral dimension exceeds $8R$. Only in these cases, the force-indentation data are not affected by the sample's dimensions. These findings are fully consistent with the

physical considerations discussed in Section 3.2.

4. Discussion

The assumption that a material behaves as an elastic half-space under spherical indentation is a cornerstone in contact mechanics, especially in the context of atomic force microscopy (AFM). Nevertheless, this approximation is not universally valid and should be critically assessed, particularly for samples with finite lateral dimensions or when indentation depths become significant. Similar considerations regarding boundary effects have been discussed in a recent study on plane-strain cylindrical indentation [58]. In Section 3.1, a detailed analytical investigation of the deformation field induced by a rigid spherical indenter on an elastic substrate was conducted. The expressions for surface deflection inside and outside the contact area—given by Eqs. (6)

Fig. 7. Interface deformation near contact point for several different forces ($L_r = L_z = 10R$). a) $F = 1.07 \times 10^{-8}$ (N), b) $F = 2.13 \times 10^{-8}$ (N), c) $F = 4.27 \times 10^{-8}$ (N), d) $F = 6.40 \times 10^{-8}$ (N), e) $F = 8.54 \times 10^{-8}$ (N) (Images used courtesy of ANSYS, Inc.).

Fig. 8. Deformation of the free surface. Simulation results for indentation depth (h) as a function of the applied normal force magnitude (F); comparison between geometries of various radii (in all cases $L_r = L_z = 10R$).

Fig. 9. Applied normal force F as a function of the indentation depth h : comparison between simulation results, analytical predictions based on Eq. (4), and experimental AFM data obtained on an agarose gel with a Young's modulus of approximately 100 kPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.5. The close agreement among the three datasets validates the accuracy of the numerical model in capturing the elastic contact behavior.

and (8)—were recast in terms of a dimensionless function, $\Omega(r)$, allowing a systematic study of the spatial decay of deformation as a function of radial distance from the contact center.

Two characteristic regimes were analyzed: shallow and deeper indentations. For shallow indentations (i.e., $h \leq 0.1R$), it was shown that at a distance of $r = 4R$, the surface deflection falls to just 7% of its value at the contact radius. This suggests that for such indentation depths, any sample with lateral dimensions exceeding $4R$ can be reliably modeled as an elastic half-space. By contrast, for deeper indentations (up to $h \approx 0.6R$), the deformation remains significant over a wider lateral extent. As derived in Section 3.1, the contact radius increases nonlinearly with h , and at $r = 8R$, the deflection is still about 7% of the value at the contact edge. Consequently, for deeper indentations, the material must possess lateral dimensions at least eight times greater than

the indenter radius for the half-space assumption to hold. In all simulations, the sample's height was considered to be large ($L_z = 10R$) to avoid the possibility of substrate effects. The indentation depth is naturally constrained by the sample thickness. According to Bueckle's rule, commonly applied in conventional nanoindentation, the maximum indentation should not exceed 10% of the sample thickness to avoid substrate effects [40,59]. In our simulations and experiments, the maximum indentation depth was approximately $0.6R$, satisfying $h < L_z/10$. In Fig. 10b, simulations for samples with $L_r = 10R$ and different thicknesses, ranging from $L_z = 4R$ to $L_z = 10R$, were performed. As the sample thickness increases, the force-indentation data converge to those expected for an elastic half-space.

These findings reinforce a key insight: the validity of the elastic half-space approximation is depth-dependent and intimately tied to the geometric configuration of the sample. Importantly, this limitation is often overlooked in standard analyses of AFM indentation data. To validate and complement the analytical predictions, FEM simulations were performed using samples of finite radius and fixed height ($L_z = 10R$), with lateral radii ranging from $L_r = 2R$ to $L_r = 10R$. These simulations, illustrated in Figs. 7–10, provide a spatially resolved view of the deformation field under increasing loading conditions. As the applied force increased, a predictable expansion of both the contact radius and the surrounding deformation was observed.

Fig. 7 revealed that deformation is highly localized under the indenter at low forces, but it spreads laterally as the indentation deepens. These results corroborate the analytical trends derived from the Ω -function analysis. In particular, the simulations emphasize that while the magnitude of vertical displacement drops off with radial distance, it remains non-negligible unless the lateral extent of the sample is sufficiently large. The color gradient representing vertical displacements further emphasizes how stress fields propagate away from the contact zone in a nontrivial manner, especially at higher indentation forces.

Determining the validity of the elastic half-space assumption in AFM research is crucial for obtaining reliable mechanical measurements, especially when probing samples with limited lateral dimensions. Many contact mechanics models used in AFM assume that the sample extends infinitely in all directions, an approximation that may not hold when testing small biological structures such as individual proteins or sub-cellular features. In such cases, the finite size of the probed region can influence the force-indentation response, leading to inaccuracies in calculated parameters like Young's modulus. Verifying the conditions under which the half-space assumption remains applicable allows researchers to correctly interpret mechanical data and avoid systematic errors in nanoscale studies where spatial confinement is inherent.

Since the theoretical considerations presented in Section 3.1 were validated by the simulation results, the presented theoretical analysis can be used to further test the minimum lateral dimensions of the tested samples for the elastic half-space approximation to remain valid. The criterion used is that the deflection of the sample's free surface should decrease to 7% of its value at the contact radius. This threshold was chosen based on the simulation results presented in Section 3.2, which showed that when the sample dimensions correspond to the region where the deflection drops to 7%, the force-indentation data remain nearly unaffected. More specifically, the choice of this threshold was based on an empirical approach derived from Eq. (10). For $\frac{r}{r_c} = 4\sqrt{10}$, Eq. (10) yields $\Omega \approx 0.11$, which corresponds to 7% of the value $\Omega = \pi/2$ at $r = r_c$. Using Eq. (12), this condition gives $r/R = 4$, leading to the simple rule $r \geq 4R$. For comparison, a 10% threshold ($\Omega \approx 0.16$) results in $\frac{r}{r_c} = 2.7\sqrt{10}$ and $r/R = 2.7$, producing an excessively small lateral sample, while a 5% threshold ($\Omega \approx 0.08$) gives $\frac{r}{r_c} = 5.3\sqrt{10}$ and $r/R = 5.3$ corresponding to an excessively large one. Simulations presented in Fig. 10 confirm that when $r/R = 4$, the data follow the Hertzian equation for small indentation depths. A similar analysis for larger indentation depths showed that the 7% threshold leads to a simple rule, $r \geq 8R$, which was also confirmed through FEM simulations.

Fig. 10. (a) Simulation results showing the applied normal force (F) as a function of the indentation depth (h) for specimens with varying lateral dimensions (ranging from $L_r = 2R$ to $L_r = 10R$). In all cases $L_z = 10R$. The results illustrate the influence of the sample's lateral size on the force-indentation response and assess the validity of the elastic half-space approximation under different sample's dimensions. (b) Simulation results showing the applied normal force (F) as a function of indentation depth (h) for specimens of varying thickness (ranging from $L_z = 4R$ to $L_z = 10R$). In all cases $L_r = 10R$.

Therefore, the 7 % threshold offers both an easy-to-remember limit and accuracy within the Hertzian regime. It is also interesting to note that using the analysis presented in Section 3.1, it was found that for a maximum indentation depth equal to $0.02 R$, a sample with lateral dimensions equal to $1.7 R$ can be considered an elastic half-space. This is a very interesting result concerning experiments on very small samples (e. g., a protein, fibril, or virus).

It is also important to note the approximations employed in this paper. First, the indenter was modeled as a perfect sphere—a common simplification in AFM indentation analyses that allows the direct application of Hertzian contact mechanics. In reality, AFM tips may exhibit manufacturing imperfections, wear, or contamination, which can locally alter the contact geometry and slightly modify the deformation field. Such deviations are most significant at shallow indentation depths, where local stress concentrations near tip irregularities may influence the measured force-indentation response. However, for the indentation depths considered in typical AFM experiments, the contact area is generally larger than typical tip defects, so the overall elastic response remains primarily governed by the nominal spherical geometry. Consequently, the use of an idealized spherical indenter provides a valid approximation of the mechanical behavior.

Another interesting issue to discuss is that small deviations in the Poisson's ratio slightly affect the absolute deflection of the elastic surface, as shown by Eqs. (6) and (8), where the deflection is proportional to $1 - \nu^2$. For example, a Poisson's ratio of 0.48 results in a 2.6 % difference in deflection compared to that obtained when assuming $\nu = 0.5$. However, our analysis is based on the ratio $\frac{y_{out}(r)}{y_0}$, where $y_{out}(r)$ is the deflection at a given distance (e.g., $r = 4R$) and y_0 is the deflection at $r = r_c$. For small indentation depths, when $r = 4R$ and $\Omega \cong 0.11$, this ratio equals 0.07, meaning the deflection is 7 % of its value at $r = r_c$. Importantly, the ratio $\frac{y_{out}(r)}{y_0}$ is independent of both the Poisson's ratio and the indenter radius ensuring that our results are robust against deviations in these parameters.

It is also important to note that biological samples are highly heterogeneous at the nanoscale, which may raise concerns regarding the applicability of Hertzian mechanics. However, recent studies have demonstrated that Hertzian equations can be applied to heterogeneous

materials, with the fitting parameter representing an average or depth-dependent 'apparent' Young's modulus [48,49,60]. Thus, fitting force-indentation data to the Hertz equation (Eq. (1)) is mathematically valid, and the resulting modulus reflects the overall mechanical properties at the specific indentation depth, supporting the applicability of our methodology to heterogeneous samples [48,49,60]. It should be noted that this approach assumes gradual spatial variations in mechanical properties, as is typical for soft biological tissues. In cases of extreme heterogeneity, more localized or multi-scale models may be necessary. For instance, at large indentation depths or in the presence of pronounced nonlinear behavior, the force-indentation analysis can employ polynomial or hyperelastic models, replacing the linear Hertzian approximation. Additionally, for viscoelastic effects, time-dependent models, such as the standard linear solid or generalized Maxwell models, can be integrated with AFM indentation protocols. Performing indentations at multiple loading rates allows the extraction of both instantaneous (elastic) and time-dependent (viscous) contributions, representing a promising direction for future studies on complex biological materials.

Another relevant point is the omission of adhesion. The present analysis and simulations consider an idealized rigid sphere indenting an elastic half-space without surface forces. This approach is consistent with common AFM practice for biological samples, where several strategies minimize adhesion effects. For instance, AFM probes are often passivated with non-adhesive compounds, such as polyethylene glycol, and measurements are frequently conducted in liquid environments to mimic physiological conditions. In such settings, adhesion forces are typically one to two orders of magnitude smaller than those measured in air [61–64]. While specific tip-sample interactions, such as electrostatic or chemical bonding, may still occur, their contribution is minor relative to the elastic forces analyzed here. Moreover, the indentation depths considered often exceed the range where adhesion dominates, ensuring that elastic contributions remain the primary factor [64]. Future work will extend the model to incorporate cases with stronger adhesion, allowing investigation of tip-sample interactions where adhesive forces are non-negligible.

In addition, an important extension of the present work should be the systematic investigation of finite-thickness effects in AFM indentation.

For samples with limited thickness, classical Hertzian contact models require appropriate correction functions [65,66]. Future studies will aim to determine the combined influence of lateral dimensions and sample thickness on the applicability of modified Hertz equations, potentially refining criteria such as $r \geq 4R$ for thin samples. This research will help establish guidelines for AFM indentation experiments on soft materials with finite dimensions.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the combined analytical and numerical investigations presented in this paper provide a rigorous framework for evaluating the half-space assumption in AFM nanoindentation with spherical indenters. The results establish quantitative geometric thresholds for the sample radius relative to indenter size and penetration depth, offering practical guidance for experimental design and data interpretation. For shallow indentations, lateral dimensions of 4 R suffice, while for deeper indentations (up to 0.6 R), dimensions of at least 8 R are required. Beyond these limits, deviations from half-space behavior become significant and must be treated with caution. These insights can enhance the reliability and physical relevance of nanomechanical measurements, particularly in fields where precision is paramount, such as AFM nanoindentation on soft biomaterials and biological materials.

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